

The Relationship Between Parental Attachment and Aggressive Behaviours Among In-School Adolescents in Anambra State, Nigeria

Okeke, Nkechi Uzochukwu (Ph.D)¹ & Anierobi, Elizabeth Ifeoma²

Department of Educational Foundations,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka
drnkechiokeke@gmail.com

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4055779>

Abstract

Parental responses lead to the development of patterns of attachment, these in turn, lead to internal working models which will guide the individual's feelings, thoughts and expectations in later relationship. This study was carried out to determine the relationship between parental attachment and aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state. Four null hypotheses stated in the null form guided the study. Correlation research design was adopted for the study. The study was carried out in Anambra state using 18 secondary schools randomly selected from the six educational zones. The population consist all SS 1,2 and 3 students from the chosen schools. 450 students were drawn from each school (that is, 150 from SS1, 2 and 3 respectively) given a total of 8,100. The sample of the study stood at 1,320 students who showed aggressive behaviours after responding to aggressive questionnaire developed by Buss and Perry (1992). A researcher developed instrument was used for the study titled "Parental Attachment Questionnaire (PAQ). Validity of the instrument was determined by three experts in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach Alpha and an alpha coefficient of 0.79 was obtained which was considered high, therefore, the instrument was considered reliable for use. Findings of the study revealed that secure parent-child attachment has no positive relationship with aggressive behaviours in adolescents among others. It was recommended that educational psychologists and school counselors should give adequate attention to family counseling as this will assist parents to adjust to a more proactive parent-child attachment which will enhance adolescent's behaviour.

Key words: Parental attachment, aggressive behaviours, adolescents

Introduction

One of the most primary associations that an individual forms in life is with caregivers or parents. Parents play an imperative role in child development like upbringing, fulfilling basic needs, providing economical support, acting as models from where they learn independent functioning, moral development, social exposure and interaction among others. Young children

need to develop a relationship with at least one primary caregiver for normal social and emotional development. Kennedy and Kennedy (2004) assert that infants become attached to adults who are sensitive and responsive in social interactions with them and who remain as consistent caregivers for some months during the period from about 6 months to 2 years of age. During the later part of this period, children begin to use attachment figures (familiar people) as a secure base to explore from and return to.

Attachment between adolescence and parents develops naturally with time, as the children who developed a strong need to remain near their parents were the ones who were most likely to survive both physically and psychologically. Attachment does not develop suddenly and unheralded but rather emerges in a series of steps, moving from a child's real partnership with his/her parents. Children who have developed an attachment to their parents, most probably wanted to maintain their parents' affection and approval and so are motivated to adopt the standard of behavior that the parents set for them.

Armed with conflicting philosophies, every parent tests different approaches to see what ultimately works for the parent and the children. Attachment is one specific aspect of the relationship between a child and a parent with its purpose being to make a child safe, secure and protected. Parental attachment focuses on the nurturing connection that parents can develop with their children. That nurturing connection is viewed as ideal way to raise secure, independent and empathetic children. Parents everywhere seek a close emotional bond with their children. They also strive to develop a parenting style that works with their values.

In Igbo traditional society where the researchers came from, some parenting models favor treating children as little adults to be reasoned with. Others take an approach that stresses rule-following. They all aim to create self-reliant adults who can maintain healthy relationships and go on to have families of their own. Remember that everything you do is an example for your children. When you drink or send your son to buy you cigarettes, you are already introducing him to that lifestyle. When your children see you having an affair with a strange woman, you are sowing a terrible seed in their hearts. The way you talk to their mother is probably how your sons will talk to their wives too. The low esteem of their mother due to how you treat her will probably become the self-esteem of their daughters too.

In the context of this work, aggressive behaviour implies an observable behaviour targeted at harming another person ranging from minor to serious injuries. Parental attachment explains the quality of care a child gets from his/her caregiver and these boards on the extent of satisfaction of his needs by his caregivers.

Benoit (2004) noted that the quality of attachment that an infant develops with a specific caregiver is largely determined by the caregiver's response to the infant when the infant's attachment system is "activated" example when the infant's feelings of safety and security are threatened, such as when he/she is ill, physically hurt or emotionally upset, particularly frightened. Benoit enumerated 4 types of child-parent attachment. They include Secure, avoidant, resistant and disorganized. Evergreen Psychotherapy center (2017) also noted 4 (four) child-parent attachment styles namely Secure-autonomous, avoidant-dismissing, anxious-preoccupied and disorganized-unresolved. Supporting the above, Kennedy and Kennedy (2004) pointed 4

(four) child-parent attachment styles as Secure, anxious-avoidant, anxious-resistant and disorganized.

Kennedy et al (2004) noted that children exposed to secure parental attachment are generally more likely to see others as supportive and helpful and themselves as competent and worthy of respect. These children relate positively to others and display resilience, engage in complex play and are more successful in the classroom and in interactions with other children. They are better at taking the perspectives of others and have more trust in others. Anxious-avoidant parental attachment children as opined by Duschinsky (2015) are generally less effective in managing stressful situations. They are likely to withdraw and resist seeking help which inhibits them from forming satisfying relationships with others. These children show more aggression and antisocial behaviour like lying, bullying and they tend to distance themselves from others to reduce emotional stress. Anxious-resistant attachment children are on the opposite end of the spectrum from anxious-avoidant children. They lack self confidence and stick close to their primary caregivers. They may display exaggerated emotional reactions and keep their distance from their peers, leading to social isolation. Children exposed to disorganized parental attachment usually fail to develop an organized strategy for coping with separation distress and tend to display aggression, disruptive behaviours and social isolation.

Parental attachment is based on the idea that children learn to trust and thrive when their needs are consistently met by a caregiver in life. Children who never experience this secure attachment early in their life according to proponents do not learn to form healthy attachments in life (<https://www.webmd.com>parenting>). Supporting the above, Main, Hesse and Hesse (2011) utilizing adult attachment interview developed, she found that unresolved trauma and loss in a parent's life is the best predictor of disorganized attachment between a parent and child. Main noted that parents who have experienced trauma in their early lives and have not resolved that trauma by feeling the full pain of their childhoods and making sense of it are likely to engage in disorienting behaviour with their child. Main further opined that it is not necessarily how bad someone's childhood was that impacts attachment between parent and child, but how much they have been able to make sense out of the feelings and full pain of their past creating a coherent narrative. The better able someone is to resolve trauma and conflict from their early life the better able they will be to form a secure attachment.

Benoit (2004) opine that attachment is distinguished from other aspects of parenting such as disciplining, entertaining and teaching. Benoit said that attachment is where the child uses the primary caregiver as a secure base from which to explore and when necessary as a haven of safety and a source of comfort.

Kendra (2019) viewed attachment as a special emotional relationship that involves an exchange of comfort, care and pleasure. Kendra noted that a child's attachment is largely influenced by their primary caregiver's sensitivity to their needs. Parents who consistently (or almost always) respond to their children's need would create securely attached children, such children are certain that their parents will be responsive to their needs and communications.

From the foregoing, parental attachment is quite clearly based on a bi-directional social psychological interaction of a child with primary caregivers who it is anticipated can provide a

secure, safe base from which to explore. Parental attachment has been considered a crucial phenomenon in relations between adolescents and parents and has been found to have a direct, positive influence on the well-being outcomes of adolescents.

Adolescence as noted by Mihalyi (2020) is a transitional phase of growth and development between childhood and adulthood. The World Health Organization defines an adolescent as any person between ages 10 and 19. Adolescence is a time of fluctuating and rapidly changing interests and desires, high energy, sexual maturation, physical growth and limited emotional insight. This creates fertile ground for many emotional problems and challenges that might benefit from professional intervention (psychology glossary- AlleyDog.com).

Adolescence is understood in broader terms that encompass psychological, social and moral terrain as well as the strictly physical aspects of maturation (<https://www.britanica.com>science>). Adolescence is a transitional stage of physical and psychological development that generally occurs during the period from puberty to legal adulthood. Adolescence is a stage of life in the development of an individual which is between childhood and adulthood occasioned by physical changes called puberty. Adolescents stage pose a lot of concern world-wide to the individual himself, parents, teachers', in fact to the caregivers (Mawson, Bestwith, Dingle & Lubman, 2015).

Aggression among adolescents today is on the increase and we continue to hear reports of aggressive behaviours such as pushing, hitting, fighting, bullying, molesting junior ones as well as indirect aggression which include telling lies to get colleagues in trouble in secondary schools in Anambra state. Steven (2020) explained aggression as a range of behaviours that can result in both physical and psychological harm to yourself, others or objects in the environment. He opined that this type of behaviour centers on harming another person either physically or mentally. Aggression is a behaviour that is intended to harm another individual who does not wish to be harmed. Intentional harm is however perceived as worse than unintentional harm, even when the harms are identical (Ames & Fiske, 2013).

Bushman and Huesmann (2010) assert that in few hundred years ago, aggression was an adaptive behaviour for our ancient ancestors who lived in small group where by male used aggression to gain access to females, food, shelter and other resources, females will use aggression to defend their offspring and gain resources for them. Bushman et al noted that aggression nowadays, is defined as behaviours that can be seen and are intended to harm others which involve at least two people. Most social psychologists define aggression as any behaviour that is intended to harm another person who wants to avoid the harm. This definition includes three important features: First, aggression is a behaviour, you can see it. Second, aggression is intentional, it is not accidental. Third, the victim wants to avoid the harm (social psychology.iresearchnet.com).

The researchers' experience having taught for some years in secondary school, shows that often students resort to these aggressive acts at the slightest provocation. They see these acts as the first resort to solving conflicts. This poses a great concern because most often serious injuries are sustained and casualties rushed to the hospital. So many reasons could be given for such

aggressive behaviours like exposure to social media, mental or health conditions, substance use disorders, spiritual problems among others.

Human behaviours can be learned and strengthening by observing the behaviours of others, and the consequences of that behaviour, rather than experiencing the reinforcement or consequences directly. Bandura also stressed that aggressive behaviour can be learned through observation. Through modeling, a child can learn a behaviour that they have never performed or displayed previously by observing the behavior of a model and repeating the behaviour themselves. In a classic Bandura's Bobo Doll studies, it was revealed that children tend to model the aggressive acts and act aggressively towards the Bobo Doll after watching the adult hit and kick the Bobo Doll (Bandura, Ross & Ross, 1963 in Schultz & Schultz, 2009). This experiment as opined by Schultz et al proved that aggressive behaviour of a person can be learned through observation of aggressive acts which happened from their living environment such as television and parents aggressive behaviours.

Although human behaviour can be learned through observation of other people's behaviour, but the truth remains that for the child to perform and maintain the behaviour which he has learnt depends on the reward and punishment contingencies that the child receives. This indicates that an adolescent is more likely to behave aggressively if he/she experiences positive outcome from his aggressive acts. In other words, there is likelihood of the adolescent performing the aggressive acts in future when the outcome of such aggressive acts was repeatedly met with positive approvals and this is where parental attachment comes in. In short, social learning approaches, principles of observational learning, learning through reinforcement and experience, explain the mechanism leading to development of aggression.

In psychology, young children need to develop a relationship with at least one primary caregiver for normal social and emotional development. During the later part of their life, adolescents begin to use attachment figures as a secure base to explore from or return to. Parental responses lead to the development of patterns of attachment, these in turn, lead to internal working models which will guide the individual's feelings, thoughts and expectations in later relationship. It is against this background that the researchers investigated empirically the relationship between parental attachment and aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state.

Statement of the Problem

Attachment is a universal human need that leads to the formation of close bonds of affection. Children become attached to familiar people who respond to their needs for physical care and stimulation. Attachment between adolescence and parents develops naturally with time and not suddenly. Children who have developed an attachment to their parents, most probably wanted to maintain their parents' affection and approval and so are motivated to adopt the standard of behaviour that the parents set for them. Much of the existing literatures concerning attachment focused on the positive relationship between parents and adolescents as an important dimension in enhancing academic development, preventing achievement-related and educational problems. Little empirical evidence has been reported however, on the relationship

between parental attachment and aggressive behaviour among adolescents. Consequently, the main goal of this study is to examine the relationship between parental attachment and aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state.

The study was guided by four hypotheses stated in null form which include:

1. There is no significant relationship between disorganized attachment style and aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state.
2. Anxious-avoidant attachment style is not a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state.
3. Secure attachment style does not predict aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state.
4. Anxious-resistant attachment style has no significant predictive power on aggressive behaviours of in-school adolescents in Anambra state.

Method

The study adopted correlation research design. Nworgu (2015) assert that a correlation research design seeks to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables. The population of the study comprised all the senior secondary school (SSS 1, 2 & 3) students in Anambra state of Nigeria. There are six educational zones in Anambra state namely: Awka, Ogidi, Otuocha, Nnewi, Aguata and Onitsha. A total of 8,100 senior secondary school students who were drawn through multi-stage sampling technique, from 18 schools in Anambra state were used for the study. The researchers stratified all the secondary schools in the state into 6 educational zones. Using simple random sampling technique, 3 schools were drawn from each educational zone, giving a total of 18 schools. Again, 450 students were drawn from each of the selected schools (ie 150 students from SS 1, 150 students from SS2 and 150 students from SS3). The choice of the senior secondary school students was based on information obtained from interview session held with the school authorities precisely form teachers, guidance counselors and the principals who establish that most of the reported aggressive behaviours come from the senior students. The researchers tried to establish aggressive students by administering an aggressive questionnaire developed by Buss and Perry (1992) on them. The aggression scale consists of 4 factors: physical aggression (PA), verbal aggression (VA), anger (A), and hostility (H). The students were sincerely assured that the questionnaire was strictly for research and academic purpose and not for taking any disciplinary actions on them. This assurance empowered the students' honesty in filling the questionnaire. Buss and Perry's aggression instrument consist of 29 items with the break down as follows: Physical aggression = 9 items, verbal aggression = 5 items, anger = 7 items and hostility = 8 items. The inventory used a likert answering system. Respondents/students were asked to select the choice that best suited them from the following options: extremely characteristic (5), somewhat characteristic (4), neither uncharacteristic (3), somewhat uncharacteristic (2) extremely uncharacteristic (1).

The study reliability was confirmed by repeating the test and calculating the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient ($r = 0.79$). The Cronbach reliability coefficient of the

scale was found to be 0.70. At the end of the test, 1,320 students (representing 16.3% of the entire population) who showed aggressive behaviours were selected for the study.

Three different instruments were used for data collection. They were: Buss and Perry's (1992) aggression instrument, interview schedule and researchers constructed questionnaire titled "Parental Attachment Questionnaire" (PAQ). The instrument was administered on 1,320 students who showed aggressive behaviours. The respondents were asked to simply tick against the statement that best explains their attachment to their primary caregivers (parents). It consist of 40 items covering the 4 parental attachment styles. The instrument was structured in a 5-point likert fashion ranging from very much, quite a bit, moderate amount, somewhat to not at all. The instrument was subjected to validation process. The validity of the instrument was determined by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was determined using cronbach alpha with overall reliability coefficient of 0.79. The instrument was administered to the chosen sample for the study with the aid of three trained research assistants.

Data collected for the study were analyzed using regression analysis to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels. The regression statistics were based on American Psychological Association (APA) format of presenting regression analysis, where the unstandardized beta (b) represents the slope of the line between the predictor variable and the independent variable; standardized beta (B) represents the correlation coefficient; t-test statistics (t) used to calculate the p-value of the predictor; and probability level (p) shows whether or not the independent variable significantly predicts the dependent variable.

Results

Table 1: Result of Students Response to Buss and Perry's Aggression Questionnaire

No. of Items	Response	Frequency	Percentage
29 items	Extremely characteristic(5)	1,320	16.3%
	Somewhat characteristic(4)	1,064	13.1%
	Neither uncharacteristic (3)	1,880	23.2%
	Somewhat uncharacteristic(2)	2,096	25.9%
	Extremely uncharacteristic(1)	1,740	21.5%

N= 8,100

From the above table, Buss and Perry's aggression instrument was administered on 8,100 students. 1,320 representing 16.3% of the entire population who showed aggressive behaviours were used for the study.

Table 2: Regression Table Showing the Relationship between Parental Attachment and Aggressive Behaviours of In-School Adolescents in Anambra State.

Model	Independent variable	Dependent variable	B	Standard error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	Disorganized parental Attachment Style	Physical aggression	0.38	0.08		0.37	.000
		Verbal aggression	0.58	0.07		0.54	.000
		Anger		0.45	0.09		.000
		Hostility	0.39	0.07	0.38	5.26	.000
2	Anxious-avoidant Attachment Style	Physical aggression	4.86	4.73		0.35	1.03
		Verbal aggression	0.32	0.92		0.30	4.55
		Anger		0.49	0.09		0.40
		Hostility	0.32	0.92	0.30	4.55	.000
3	Secure Parental Attachment Style	Physical aggression	0.14	0.09		0.13	.113
		Verbal aggression	0.22	0.08		0.21	.008
		Anger	0.19	0.07	0.21	2.76	.006
		Hostility	0.14	0.09	0.13	1.59	.113
4	Anxious-resistant Parental Attachment Style	Physical aggression	0.28	0.85		0.23	3.27
		Verbal aggression	3.87	0.95		0.28	4.00
		Anger	4.93	1.66	0.36	6.95	.000
		Hostility	0.31	0.07	0.34	4.56	.000

Table 2 above shows the 4 parental attachment styles (disorganized, anxious-avoidant, anxious-resistant and secure) and their relationship/predictive power on the 4 factors: Physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger and hostility. Model 1 shows that disorganized parental attachment style is significantly related to aggressive behaviors of in-school adolescents in Anambra state. Disorganized parental attachment style had a significant relationship on all the 4 factors ie physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger and hostility. Its strength of relationship on

physical aggression (B=0.38, B=0.37, t=5.06, p<=.000); Verbal aggression (B=0.58, B= 0.54, t=7.93, p<=.000); Anger (B= 0.45, B= 0.44, t= 5.49, p<=.000) and Hostility (B=0.39, B= 0.38, t= 5.26, p<=.000). The unstandardized beta (B) scores = 0.38, 0.58, 0.45 and 0.39 for physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger and hostility respectively. The standardized beta (B) reveals a high correlation coefficient between disorganized parental attachment style and physical aggression (B=0.37), verbal aggression (B=0.54), anger (B=0.44) and hostility (B=0.38). The strength of relationship is shown by p<=.000 showing a highly significant relationship between disorganized parental attachment style and aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state. Therefore, null hypothesis 1 which states that there is no significant relationship between disorganized parental attachment style and aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state is rejected and the alternative accepted.

Table 2 model 2 shows that anxious-avoidant parental attachment style positively predicted aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state. Anxious-avoidant parental attachment style had a significant relationship on all the 4 factors measured ie physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger and hostility. Its predictive strength on Physical aggression (B=4.86, B=0.35, t= 1.03, p<=.000); Verbal aggression (B= 0.19, B= 0.21, t=2.76, p<= 0.06); Anger (B= 0.49, B= 0.40, t=5.26, p<=.000) and Hostility (B=0.32, B= 0.30, t= 4.55, p<=.000). The unstandardized beta (B) scores for physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger and hostility were 4.86, 0.19, 0.49 and 0.32 respectively. The standardized beta (B) shows a high positive correlation coefficient between anxious-avoidant parental attachment style to physical aggression (B=0.35), verbal aggression (B=0.21), anger (B=0.40) and hostility (B=0.30) respectively. P<=.000 in each case shows significant relationship between anxious-avoidant parental attachment style and aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state. Null hypothesis 2 is therefore rejected and the alternative accepted.

Model 3 in table 2 above reveals that secure parental attachment style is not significantly related to aggressive behaviors of in-school adolescents. Secure parental attachment style does not predict aggressive behaviors. The strength of secure parental attachment style on Physical aggression (B =0.14, B= 0.13, t= 1.59, p<= .113); Verbal aggression (B= 0.22, B= 0.21, t= 2.69, p<= .008); Anger (B=0.19, B= 0.21, t= 2.76, p<= .006) and Hostility (B =0.14, B= 0.13, t= 1.59, p< .113). The unstandardized beta scores = 0.14, 0.22, 0.19 and 0.14 for physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger and hostility respectively. The standardized beta (B) shows a low correlation coefficient between secure parental attachment style and physical aggression (B= 0.13), verbal aggression (B=0.21), anger (B=0.21) and hostility (B=0.13). The P< values of .113, .008, .006 and .113 indicates no significant relationship between secure parental attachment style and aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Aambra state. Null hypothesis 3 which states that secure parental attachment style does not predict aggressive behaviors among in-school adolescents in Anambra state is accepted and the alternative rejected.

From table 2 above, model 4 shows the relationship between anxious-resistant parental attachment style and aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state. The findings from the result in table 2 above shows that anxious-resistant parental attachment style had a significant predictive power on the 4 factors ie physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger

and hostility. Its predictive strength on Physical aggression ($B = 0.28$, $B = 0.85$, $t = 3.27$, $p < .001$); Verbal aggression ($B = 3.87$, $B = 0.28$, $t = 4.00$, $p < .005$); Anger ($B = 4.93$, $B = 0.36$, $t = 6.95$, $p < .000$) and Hostility ($B = 0.31$, $B = 0.34$, $t = 4.56$, $p < .000$). The unstandardized beta (B) = 0.28, 3.87, 4.93 and 0.31 for physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger and hostility respectively. The standardized beta (B) shows a high positive correlation coefficient between anxious-resistant parental attachment style to physical aggression ($B = 0.23$), verbal aggression ($B = 0.28$), anger ($B = 0.36$) and hostility ($B = 0.34$). The strength of prediction is shown by $P < .001$, $.005$, $.000$ and $.000$ respectively which indicates a highly predictive power of anxious-resistant parental attachment style on aggressive behaviours of in-school adolescents in Anambra state. Therefore, null hypothesis 4 which states that anxious-resistant parental attachment style has no significant predictive power on aggressive behaviours of in-school adolescents in Anambra state is rejected and the alternative accepted.

Discussion

Findings of the study showed that disorganized parental attachment style is significantly related to aggressive behaviours of in-school adolescents. The result is supported by the findings of Kennedy and Kennedy (2004) that children with a disorganized attachment usually fail to develop an organized strategy for coping with separation, distress and tend to display aggression, disruptive behaviours and social isolation. Kennedy et al further assert that children with a disorganized attachment are more likely to see others as threats than sources of support and thus may switch between social withdrawal and defensively aggressive behaviors. Goodman, Stroh and Bartlett (2013) research supported the idea that the attachment style with an individual's care giver can influence aggression levels in adulthood. They conducted a study with 56 children between the ages of 5 to 10 and their mothers. After all tests were completed, a multiple regression analysis was calculated on all variables. Their tests proved significant at the $p < .001$ level. The hypothesis that the mother's borderline feature, specifically identify diffusions primitive defenses were positively correlated with their children's disorganized attachment representations. Finally, the findings of the study align with that of Lisa (2015) which revealed that individuals with a disorganized attachment often cannot make sense of their experiences. Lisa noted that they may have trouble socially or struggle in using others to co-regulate their emotions. Because they struggle with poor social and emotional regulation skills, may find it difficult to form and sustain solid relationships. They often have difficulty managing stress and may even demonstrate hostile or aggressive behaviours. Lisa concludes by saying that because of their early life experiences, they may see the world as an unsafe place.

The findings of the study revealed that anxious-avoidant parental attachment is a significant predictor of aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents. This result is supported by the findings of Konishi and Hymel (2014) who conducted a research to find a link between the attachment among father, mother and child to the adolescents level of aggression. In their research, participants of 776 students from grade 8-12 were selected. The student's age ranged from 13-19 years and came from a variety of ethnic backgrounds. The participants were given two questionnaires that assessed their demographic background, anger and parental

attachment. Their result indicated that aggressiveness correlated with an anxious-avoidant attachment. Similarly, the finding is supported by Koruklu & Asyan (2017) who observed that children who had anxious-avoidant attachments are prone to have emotional and behavioural problems in future. Koruklu et al noted that anxious-avoidant individuals perceive people around them negatively compared to secure attached individuals, and are more angry and aggressive toward people around them. They assert that aggressive behaviours especially during adolescence are based on insecure attachment. They observed that individuals who had secure attachments established positive relationships with their peers, had better social competencies and were popular among their peers while insecure attached individuals on the other hand had negative relationships with peers due to their lower social and emotional competencies. The findings of this study also agrees with that of Duschinsky (2015) that children with an anxious-avoidant attachment are generally less effective in managing stressful situation. They are likely to withdraw and resist seeking help, which inhibits them from forming satisfying relationships with others. Kennedy et al assert that children with an anxious-avoidant attachment show more aggression and antisocial behaviours like lying, bullying and they tend to distance themselves from others to reduce emotional stress.

Furthermore, it was revealed from the findings of the study that secure parental attachment does not predict aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents. The findings of this study agreed with findings of Goodman et al (2013); Akinyi, Odongo and Aloka (2019) as well as Erdem (2017) that children who perceived their parents as caring reported fewer tendencies of aggressive acts. It also agrees with the findings of Bloodworth (2017) that the relationship between a child and his/her primary caregiver can have a positive or negative correlation with the behaviour emitted. In a study Bloodworth conducted with 100 students from Mckendree university to see if the attachment style an individual has with their primary caregiver as a child influences their aggression level as adult, her result indicated that a negative relationship existed if a person had a secure attachment, then he/she had less aggressive behaviour. The findings of this study also aligns with the findings of Akinyi et al that there is significant negative relationship between parent-child secure attachment and relational aggression among pre-schoolers. This finding as they observed implies that first, a pre-school child who enjoys a secure attachment with his/her parents would less likely have an aggressive tendencies towards other people or his/her peers. Secondly, secure attachment prevents the occurrence of aggression among pre-school children. Kendra (2019) supporting the findings of this study assert that parents of securely attached children tend to play more with their children. Additionally, these parents react more quickly to their children's needs and are more responsive to their children than the parents of insecurely attached children. Kendra noted that securely attached children are more empathetic during later stages of childhood. These children are also less disruptive, less aggressive and more mature than children with avoidant attachment. Finally, Kennedy et al (2004) supporting the findings of this study opined that securely attached children are generally more likely to see others as supportive and helpful and themselves as competent/ worthy of respect. They relate positively to others and display resilience, engage in complex play

and more successful in the classroom and in interactions with other children. They are better at taking the perspectives of others and have more trust in others.

Finally, anxious-resistant attachment has significant predictive power on aggressive behaviours among in-school adolescents in Anambra state as revealed from the findings of the study. However, the findings of this study agrees with that of Parens (2012) who carried out a 40 years longitudinal study that focused on newborns and the attachment they shared with their mothers. Paren was interested in the long-term effects of attachment and its relation to aggression. After following, interviewing and evaluating his participants for 40 years, He was able to support his hypothesis that anxious-resistant attachment had a positive correlation with aggressive behaviours that is often shown through prejudice. This study supports Konishi et al (2014) research that attachment style had an impact upon aggression throughout life, especially in adulthood. The findings of this study also agree with the findings of Duschinsky (2015) that anxious-resistant attachment children are on the opposite end of the spectrum from anxious-avoidant children. They noted that children exposed to anxious-resistant attachment likely lack self confidence and stick close to their primary caregivers. They may display exaggerated emotional reactions and keep distance from their peers, leading to social isolation.

Conclusion

Our society is threatened if we refuse to raise our children the acceptable and godly way. If that happens, we would have failed as parents. The interactions people have with their primary caregivers have an everlasting impact upon their psychological and behavioural states. These caregivers are the one who are responsible for our safety and protection, but even the slightest form of neglect can affect an individual's future. Whether the effect manifests into anti-social behaviour, troubled relationship or internal victimization there exist a commonality between childhood bonds and adulthood behaviour.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend as follows:

1. Government and churches should organize programs aimed at sensitizing parents and caregivers on the importance of good parental attachment. For example, during mother's annual august meeting, qualified, experienced and proven resource persons should be invited to educate mothers on the need for good and proper parenting and attachment.
2. Educational psychologists and school counselors should give adequate attention to family counseling. This will create awareness among parents and children on the effect of the different forms of parental attachment on the emotional and behavioural lives of individuals. This will assist parents to adjust to a more proactive parental attachment style that will enhance adolescent's behaviour.
3. The school counselors should identify at risk students from the parents susceptible of negative influence and offer appropriate therapy.

4. Parent in collaboration with the church should engage in conscious efforts to offer quality discipleship training for our children, teenagers and youths to help them grow into responsible adult and future leaders.
5. Parents should be encouraged to practice secure parent-child attachment in their homes. The school authorities during P.T.C (Parents Teachers Council) meetings should educate parents on the implication of disorganized parental attachment. This will help parents develop positive attitude and improve on their emotional and psychological well-being.

REFERENCES

- Akinyi, D.O., Odongo, B.C. & Aloka, P.J.O. (2019). Relationship between secure attachment Typed and relational aggression among pre-schoolers in Kenya. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Social Science* 5 (1) 1-6.
- AlleyDog.com- Adolescent psychology definition/ psychology glossary.
- Ames, D.L. & Fiske, S.T. (2013). Intentional harms are worse, even when they are not. *Psychological Science*, 24 (9), 1755-1762.
- Benoit, D (2004). Infant-parent attachment, definition, types, antecedents, measurement and Outcome. *Paediatrics and Child Health* (9) 541-545 (Grossmed) (Pubmed) (google scholar).
- Bloodworth, J.E. (2017). Attachment style and its influence on aggression From <https://www.mckendree.edu>
- Bushman, B.J. & Huesman, L.R. (2010). Aggression In Fiske, S.T, Gilbert, D.T. & Lindzey, G. (eds). *Handbook of Social Psychology* (5th ed) 833-863. New York, NT: Wiley & Sons.
- Buss, A.H. & Perry, M. (1992). The Buss-Perry aggression questionnaire (Aggression instrument) Retrieved from men.m.wikipedia.org.
- Duschinsky, R. (2015). The emergence of the disorganized/disoriented (D) attachment classification, 1979-1982, *History of Psychology* 18 (1) 32-46.
- Erdem, S. (2017). *Attachment to parents and resilience among high school students*. Retrieved from <https://www.semanticscholar.org>
- Evergreen Psychotherapy Center (2017). *Four styles of adult attachment*. Retrieved from <https://www.Evergreenpsychotherapy.com>
- Goodman, G., Stroh, M. & Bartlett, R. (2013). Mother's borderline feature and childrens Disorganized attachment representations as predictors of children's externalizing Behavior, *American Psychological Association* 30 (1) 16-36.
- <https://www.webmd.com/parenting-> What is attachment parenting? WebMD.

- Kendra, C. (2019). The different types of attachment styles Retrieved from <https://www.verywellmind.com>
- Kennedy, J.H. & Kennedy, C.E. (2004). Attachment theory: Implications for school Psychology, *Psychology in the Schools* (41) 247-259.doi.10.1002/pits.10153.
- Koruklu, N. & Asyan, F. (2017). The direct and indirect relationships between school Attachment, constructive conflict resolution behavior and aggression, *Journal Of Educational and Human Development* 6 (4) 57-63.
- Konishi, C. & Hymel, S. (2014). An attachment perspective on anger among adolescents, *Merrill-Palmer Quarterly* 60 (1) 52-79.
- Lisa, F. (2015). Attachment, parenting, self development and trauma. Retrieved from <https://www.psychalive.org>disorg->
- Main,M., Hesse, E. & Hesse, S. (2011). Attachment theory and research. Overview with suggested applications to child custody, *Family Court Review*, 49 (3) 426-463.
- Mihalyi,S.(2020).Adolescence/definition, characteristics and stages. Retieved from <https://www.britanica.com>science>
- Mawson, E., Best, D., Beckwith, M., Dingle, G.A. & Lubman, D.I. (2015). Social identity, social networks and recovery capital in emerging adulthood From Pmc Free Article, pubmed, google scholar.
- Nworgu, B.G. (2015). Educational research: Basic issues and methodology (3rd ed). Nsukka: University Trust Publishers.
- Parens, H. (2012). Attachment aggression and the prevention of malignant prejudice. *Psychoanalytic Inquiry*, 32, 171-185.
- Researchnet.psychology.irresearchnet.com. Aggression (social psychology).
- Schultz, D. & Schultz, S. (2009). Theories of personality (9th ed). Belmont, C.A.Wadsworth. Steven, S. (2010). Suicide and life threatening behavior. *American Association For Suicidology* (1) 30.